

Multicriteria assessment of future scenarios for the implementation of agroforestry in cereal systems

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Abstract

During the last decades of intensive agriculture, the woods, groves and hedges were destroyed to enlarge the cultivated parcels, as a result of the expansion of farms and the use of increasingly powerful agricultural equipment. This is in order to increase agricultural productivity, without taking into account the major negative impacts and environmental risks of such upheavals.

However, trees play an active role in combating erosion, especially in sensitive agricultural parcels, as well as in soil conservation by storing carbon and allowing a rich biological life in the soil. Tree rows also play an important role as windbreaks and barriers to the atmospheric diffusion of pesticides. Trees create habitat for crop pest auxiliaries, especially in areas where hedgerows and groves have long since disappeared, but they can also be a reserve for fungal or bacterial pathogens.

As part of a new TETRAE-AC²TION research project, it is proposed to evaluate the effects of tree planting in rows or around cereal plots, in the form of a multicriteria analysis to help decide the overall performance of such a system (environmental and socio-economic). This is an innovative collaborative research programme that investigates unknown environmental and socio-economic development levers for agroforestry pathways. Qualitative and quantitative criteria will make it possible to understand the impacts of such a device on the microclimate, the biodiversity, on the enrichment of the soil for the mineral nutrition of plants. However, agroforestry should also make it possible to reduce crop pathogens with a view to reducing the use of plant protection products, and to avoid the transport of pesticide molecules beyond rows of trees.

Different research teams will be mobilized to work on each of these criteria. Our multicriteria evaluation using the Electre Tri-nC and Electre III methods will allow to carry out this global evaluation of agroforestry driven systems performances, compared to conventional «intensive» systems. This study will be able to provide socio-professional stakeholders in the field with decision-making support for their change of management system, particularly those in purely conventional mode.

Keywords

Agroforestry, Field crops, Performances, Environmental risks, Multicriteria Decision Aiding

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